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A STUDY OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Teaching effectiveness means perfection, optimum level of efficiency and productivity on the part of the teacher. It refers to the height of maturity and learning that teachers grows with experience and learns more and more. This study was conducted on 148 teachers selected randomly from 8 secondary schools located in Bareilly District of Uttar Pradesh. The data was collected by self made teaching effectiveness scale. This scale consists of 38 items of 6 dimensions. Collected data was analysed using statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation and t-test. The study revealed that there is significant difference between the teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers working in secondary school. But no significant difference was found teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board female & UP Board female teachers and CBSE Board male & UP Board male teachers working in secondary schools.

Keywords- Teaching Effectiveness, Effective Teaching Skills, Teacher Performance, Effective Classroom Instructions.

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Introduction

Teacher plays significant role in the educational system. Teachers have the highest responsibility of building a nation. This fundamental duty of teacher has to be made more effective in order to mould the students effectively. Teacher has to create a good learning environment that motivates students to learn. It is firmly believed that the effectiveness of an educational institute largely determined by the quality of teachers as they interpret, imbibe and transmit knowledge and intellectual traditions from generation to generation. The importance of teacher in the process of education is of great value. "Of all the different factors, which influence the quality of education and its contribution to National Development, the quality, competence and characters of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant (Indian Education Commission 1964-66). According to Kothari D.S. "A right kind of teacher is one who possesses a vivid awareness of two missions. He not only loves his subject, but also loves whom he teaches. His success will be measured not in terms of

percentage of the result alone, but by the quality of life and character of men and women whom he has taught". Effective teacher also lead to better academic performance and all round development of the students. Teacher effectiveness is the competence and ability of a teacher to teach effectively. Teacher effectiveness is central importance to all educational institutions as it affects the process of learning and classroom management.

Over the years, researchers have attempted to identify and analyze effective and ineffective teaching. Some researchers have defined effective teaching as a complex art and a science that involves the cognitive perception, and decision- making strategies that teachers use as they plan, teach, analyze, evaluate and apply improvements to their own teaching (Costa *et. al.*, 1988; Orenstein, 1993). Other researchers have defined effective teaching in the way teachers manage their classrooms and provide appropriate instructional tasks (Fisher *et. al.*, 1978). The process of teaching in the classroom includes: choosing subject matter, lesson planning, using different methods and strategies, classroom management and evaluating student. In the academia, the quality of teaching is related to teaching effectiveness (Emery, *et. al.* 2013).

Teaching Effectiveness

When one person imparts information or skill to another person, it is common to describe the action as teaching, but not every way of bringing about learning in others counts is teaching, and not every act of teaching, curricula, infrastructure, technology, etc. It is a demanding job that requires in- depth knowledge of subject matter and age specific pedagogy. It also requires divergent skills such as creativity, leadership, organising ability, patience, administration and counselling. Elmore says- *"To improve student learning, you do not change the structure. You change the instructional practices of teachers. The schools that seem to do best are those that have a dear idea of what kind of instructional practice they wish to produce, and then design a structure to go with it."*

The origin of the word **'effective'** stems from the Latin word which means creative or productive. In contrast to efficiency, effectiveness means 'doing the right thing'. It is the capability of producing a desired result. When something is deemed effective, it means it has an intended or expected outcome, or produces a deep, vivid impression. Teaching effectiveness can be said as the power to realize socially valued objectives agreed for teachers work, especially, but not exclusively, the work concerned with enabling students to learn. It has become an adage that the effectiveness of education very much dependent on the

effectiveness of its teachers. Barr (1958) remarked “*Teacher effectiveness may be essentially a relationship between teachers, pupils and other persons concerned with educational undertaking, all affected by limiting and facilitating aspects of the immediate situation.*”

Aregbeyen, (2010) defined effective teaching as the process of making student learning possible, promote engagement and discussion, concern and respect for students and maximizing student’ academic achievement. Jahangiri, (2008) defined teaching effectiveness as ‘*the extent to which the teaching activity fulfils its intended purpose, function and goals.*’

In the present study teaching effectiveness refers to the preparation and planning for teaching, psychological basis of implementing instructions in classroom, appropriate use of teaching skills, knowledge of subject matter, teacher characteristics, classroom management, measured by the teaching effectiveness. Some of the important dimensions affecting teaching effectiveness have been summarized in Figure-1.

Fig.1. Dimensions affecting teaching effectiveness

James, k. & Sammons, P. (2016) formed a report about teaching effectiveness. This report highlights key issues and findings about two related, but distinctive topics- how to define teacher effectiveness and what is known about effective teaching practices. It also seeks to identify the implication for policymakers in education and for improving classroom practice.

Akram, S., Sufiana and Malik, K. (2012) made a research study under the topic ‘Use of audio visual aids for effective teaching of biology of secondary school level.’ The purpose of study was to explore and to compare public and private Biology at secondary school level. The

results of the study show that there is positive relationship between facility of audio visual aids and the teacher's attitude. Picard, C. J. (2014) made a research named 'Strategies for effective teaching in the twenty first century.' This study focuses on the particular needs of teachers in special education and provides suggestions and resources for improvement.

Significance of the study

Teaching effectiveness is important because effective teaching leads to effective learning of students. Effective teaching does not occur by chance. Effective teachers have become good at what they do because they evaluate their practise. Effective teaching is fundamental base of learning from lower to higher level of education. If a teacher teaches with effective manner result high gaining of knowledge, then teaching will be effective. In the present time it is main problem of our country that quality of teaching is falling day by day. Annually report of PRATHAM foundation named ASAR shows the decline status of education every year. So in the concern of quality downfall, there is great need of effective teaching and teachers both to rise up the level of teaching quality. Quality teaching may be generates if we apply methods of effective teaching with the help of effective teacher. To find out the actual states of teaching quality, firstly we have to evaluate the learning of students and teaching effectiveness of teachers in classroom. After that we may find the gaps of teaching to bring the solution of issue. So the present study is a try to evaluate the teaching effectiveness of teacher in actual classroom conditions to eradicate causes responsible for low teaching and learning quality.

Statement of the problem

A study of teaching effectiveness among secondary school teachers

Objective of the study

- 1- To study the teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers working in secondary schools.
- 2- To study the teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board female teachers and UP Board female teachers working in secondary school.
- 3- To study the teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board male teachers and UP Board male teachers working in secondary school.
- 4- To study the teaching effectiveness of UP Board male teachers and UP Board female teachers working in secondary school.

5- To study the teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board male teachers and CBSE Board female teachers working in secondary school.

Hypothesis

- H1. There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the male teachers and female teachers working in secondary school.
- H2. There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board female and UP Board female teachers working in secondary school.
- H3. There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board male and UP Board male teachers working in secondary school.
- H4. There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the UP Board male teachers and UP Board female teachers working in secondary school.
- H5. There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board male teachers and CBSE Board female teachers working in secondary school.

Delimitation of the study

The study was delimited to 148 secondary school teachers of teachers working in UP board and CBSE board secondary schools located in Bareilly district of Uttar Pradesh state only.

Methodology

The investigator randomly selected 148 teachers from 10 secondary schools located in Bareilly of Uttar Pradesh state. The sample comprised of 71 UP Board school teachers (43 male and 28 female) and 77 CBSE Board school teachers (22 male and 55 female). Survey method was used for data collection. Teaching Effectiveness Scale developed by researcher was used to collect data from sample teachers of secondary schools of Bareilly. The questionnaire consist of 38 items. The data were analysed using statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation and t- ratio.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table-1: Teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers

Table -1 given below shows descriptive statistics and t- ratio between the mean score of teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers working in secondary school.

CATEGORIES	N	MEAN	SD	T-VALUE	REMARKS
MALE	65	163.70	17.50	-3.4	SIGNIFICANT (0.01)
FEMALE	83	172.12	12.43		

It is clear from Table -1 that the mean score of female teachers is higher than male teachers and obtained t- value is significant at (0.01) level of significance. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the male teachers and female teachers working in secondary school is rejected. Result indicates that females are effective teachers than male teachers. The reason may be that the Indian women are good manager. So they manage their teaching effectively in a planned manner in classroom. Females are more responsible to targeted task and show less deviation towards their duty. There may be one more reason for the female teacher to be more effective that they are well dressed in classroom and students pay more attention with fearless environment.

Table-2: Teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board female teachers and UP Board female teachers

Table-2 given below shows descriptive statistic and t- ratio between the mean score of teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board female teachers and UP Board female teachers.

CATEGORIES	N	MEAN	SD	T-VALUE	REMARKS
CBSE BOARD FEMALE TEACHERS	55	171.21	11.97	0.92	NOT SIGNIFICANT
UP BOARD FEMALE TEACHERS	28	173.89	13.34		

From Table-2, the mean score of teaching effectiveness of UP Board female teachers was found to be higher than the mean score of CBSE Board female teachers. So the hypothesis H2, that there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board female and UP Board female teachers working in secondary school is accepted. But the mean value shows that UP Board female teachers are more effective in comparison to the CBSE Board female teachers because almost all the secondary schools which are taken for study are self financed whereas mostly UP Board schools taken for study are Government Aided. In the process of appointing teacher in UP board schools, one has to pass a tough competitive exam. Whereas CBSE board teachers are appointed on the basis of negotiations in terms of money. UP board school teachers get handsome salary so they well manage their family and career

without any depression but in CBSE board, teacher get low salary in proportion to work and time. So they could not focus their full attention towards the teaching.

Table:3 Teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board and UP Board male teachers

Table-3 given below shows descriptive ad t- ratio between the mean score of teaching effectiveness of

CATEGORIES	N	MEAN	SD	T-VALUE	REMARKS
CBSE BOARD MALE TEACHERS	22	159.68	22.42	1.33	NOT SIGNIFICANT
UP BOARD MALE TEACHERS	43	165.76	13.85		

From Table-3, the mean score of teaching effectiveness of UP Board male teachers and CBSE Board male teachers is found to be non significant. Hence the hypothesis H3, that there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board male and UP Board male teachers working in secondary school is accepted. However the teaching of UP Board male teachers was found to be effective as compared to CBSE Board male teachers. The reason may be the same as discussed in Table-2.

Table 4: Teaching effectiveness of UP Board male teachers and UP board female teachers

Table 4 given below shows descriptive statistics and t-ratio between the mean score of teaching effectiveness of UP Board Male and UP Board Female teachers.

CATEGORIES	N	MEAN	SD	T-VALUE	REMARKS
UP BOARD MALE TEACHERS	43	165.76	13.85	-2.43	SIGNIFICANT AT 0.05 LEVEL
UP BOARD FEMALE TEACHERS	28	173.89	13.34		

From Table-4, it is clear that the mean score of UP Board female teachers is higher than UP Board male teachers. There exists significant difference (at .05 levels) in UP Board male & UP Board female teachers. Hence the Hypothesis H4 that there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the UP Board male teachers and UP Board female teachers

working in secondary school is rejected. Result indicates that females are effective teachers than male. Female teachers are more effective teachers because they teach with preparation and good planning and are dedicated to their work and responsibilities.

Table 5: Teaching effectiveness between CBSE Board male and CBSE Board female teachers.

Table-5 given below shows descriptive statistics and t- ratio between the mean score of teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board male and CBSE Board female teachers.

CATEGORIES	N	MEAN	SD	T-VALUE	REMARKS
CBSE BOARD MALE TEACHERS	22	159.68	22.42	-2.89	SIGNIFICANT AT 0.01 Level
CBSE BOARD FEMALE TEACHERS	55	171.21	11.97		

From Table -5, it is clear that the mean score of CBSE Board female teachers is higher than CBSE Board male teachers. Obtained t-value is highly significant. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of the CBSE Board male teachers and CBSE Board female teachers working in secondary school is rejected. CBSE board females teachers are more effective than male teachers because females target well herself towards teaching because they are somewhat free about their career related issues but the male teachers are depressed due to their career settlement, so they don't pay full attention towards their teaching.

FIG: 2. BAR DIAGRAM SHOWS MEAN SCORE OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS-

Findings of the study

The findings of the study are as given below-

1. Female teachers of secondary school are effective then male teachers.
2. There is no significance difference in teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board female teachers and UP Board female teachers.
3. There is no significance difference in teaching effectiveness of CBSE Board male teachers and UP Board male teachers.
4. UP Board female teachers are effective than UP Board male teachers.
5. CBSE Board female teachers are effective than CBSE Board male teachers.

Conclusion

The quality and standard of education depends on the quality and standard of teachers. Mahatma Gandhi rightly pointed out that “no country can make any progress without good teachers.” Effective education can be achieved through the efforts of well qualified, competent and effective teachers. The mean score of teaching effectiveness of female teachers was found to higher than the male teachers. Thus the teaching of female teachers was found to be more effective than the male teachers.

Recommendations

Teaching is regarding as the good and noble profession. It is therefore important that those individuals who join the teaching profession should be dedicated and competent in this work. Effective teachers should take personal responsibility for students learning, determine the difficulty of lesson and provide the opportunities to students to practice newly learned concepts, give direction and control of learning, uses a variety of instructional technology and effective teaching aids. The Ministry of Education should include some teacher training

programmes in order to enhance teacher's teaching effectiveness in the classroom Teacher education programmes should provide instructions for novice teachers to increase their understanding and knowledge of teaching effectiveness.

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